

Supplemental Material

Continuum Modelling of Suffusion and Filtration in Underfilled
Gap-Graded Soils with an Immobile Skeleton

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1 Detailed Comparison of Volume Fraction Exchange Rate Models

This supplemental material provides a detailed comparison of the various erosion and deposition rate models considered in this study. In the main text, the outcomes of these various other models were aggregated and presented as a shaded region. The individual behaviour of these various models is presented and discussed in this supplemental material. The comparison considers the experimental coaxial permeameter data from [Annapareddy et al. \(2023\)](#). The sample configuration considered a mixture layer (ML) overlain by a coarse layer (CL) with upward flow triggering erosion. Suffusion is the dominant mechanism in the ML, and filtration is the dominant mechanism in the CL. Unidirectional volume exchange is considered such that only erosion is modelled in the ML (with no deposition), and purely deposition is modelled in the CL (with no erosion). The detailed comparison considers cases for the various fines content (FC15_LH1, FC20_LH1, FC25_LH1) and hydraulic loading rate (FC15_LH2, FC20_LH2, FC25_LH2).

1.1 Erosion Rate Model

The various erosion rate models considered in this study are reproduced in Table 1. Note that the erosion rate model only applies to the ML. The deposition rate model considered in the CL is the same as that considered in this study (Table 4). This isolate the influence of the erosion rate models.

Fig. 1 compares the outcomes of the various erosion rate models in capturing the fines content evolution in the ML and CL for the LH1 hydraulic loading condition. To ensure a fair comparison between the various erosion rate models, λ_e was determined by trial-and-error to ensure a reasonable fit for the outcomes of the ML and CL. Note that the same λ_e values are applied for various fines content. Fig. 1 demonstrates that for all erosion

Table 1: Erosion Rate Models

Source	Erosion Rate
This Study	$\hat{n}_e = -\lambda_e (1 - \phi) (f_c - f_{c\infty}) \overline{q_w} - \overline{q_{cr}} $
Khalil et al. (2013)	$\hat{n}_e = -\lambda_e f_c \overline{q_w} $
Cividini and Gioda (2004)	$\hat{n}_e = -\lambda_e (f_c - f_{c\infty}) \overline{q_w} $
Uzuoka et al. (2012)	$\hat{n}_e = -\lambda_e (1 - \phi) (f_c - f_{c\infty}) \overline{q_w} $

rate models, there is a plausible set of λ_e values that provide a good macro-scale fit to the experimental data. This is particularly the case for FC20_LH1 and FC25_LH1, where the normalised root mean square error (NRMSE) ranged from 1.1% to 3.9% (Table 2) across the various erosion rate models. Some discrepancies are noted for the FC15_LH1, irrespective of the choice of erosion rate model, with an over-prediction of the erosion in the ML (and consequently an over-prediction of deposition in the CL). Given that the same λ_e values are considered across varying fines content, this was attributed to the simplified model for ultimate fines content, $f_{c\infty}$ (which was the same for all erosion rate models). Table 2 shows that the NRMSE was systematically lower for the model considered in this study, with a value of 9.6% for the ML (compared with 13.4-14.9% for the other models) and a value of 4.7% for the CL (compared with 7.9-9.7% for the other models). This improvement is attributed to the consideration of critical initiation flow rate $\overline{q_{cr}}$, which effectively delayed the start of the erosion process.

Fig. 2 demonstrates that the various erosion rate models can also capture the fines content evolution in the ML and CL for the higher rate of hydraulic loading (LH2). Similarly to above, erosion in the ML for the FC15_LH2 case is over-predicted, which reinforces that the likely reason behind this is the choice of the $f_{c\infty}$ value. FC20_LH2 showed an initial burst of erosion and deposition (discussed further below when considering individual layers), which was not captured by any model. However, the fines content attained at the

end of the experiment was reasonably captured by all models. FC25_LH2 showed a good fit until 100 minutes, where the complete mixture condition was attained; none of the models considered in this study could capture this rapid transition, highlighting that this is a consequence of the immobile skeleton assumption in gap-graded underfilled soils. The NRMSE for the LH2 cases are presented in Table 2. Generally, the NRMSE values for the LH2 cases are slightly higher than that observed for the LH1 cases, and ranged from 2.9-9.4%. This is unsurprising given that the LH2 cases involved more dynamic particle movements, and reinforces the observation that the presented continuum approach is most suitable for gradual particle migration.

Figure 1: Fines content in the ML and CL for the LH1 cases. The results for each erosion rate model considered in this study are distinctly shown.

Figure 2: Fines content in the ML and CL for the LH2 cases.

Table 2: NRMSE for fines content in the ML/CL for various erosion rate models

Erosion Rate Model	FC15_LH1		FC20_LH1		FC25_LH1		FC15_LH2		FC20_LH2		FC25_LH2	
	ML	CL										
This Study	9.6	4.7	2.9	2.9	1.4	2.7	5.8	3.5	3.6	5.8	7.4	4.8
Khalil et al. (2013)	13.4	7.9	3.9	2.8	1.1	2.6	5.2	3.2	5.0	7.6	9.4	7.3
Cividini and Gioda (2004)	14.9	9.7	1.9	2.3	1.3	2.6	5.5	3.2	3.0	5.5	8.5	6.2
Uzuoka et al. (2012)	14.1	9.0	1.9	2.1	1.4	2.7	4.9	2.9	3.1	5.5	8.5	6.1

It is important to highlight that the model considered in this study did not show significant differences from a macro-scale perspective (i.e. when considering the ML and CL) compared to the other models. This was a deliberate choice; the study aimed to show that internal particle migration behaviour differs significantly for models that have the same macro-scale outcome. This is demonstrated in Figs. 3-4 which compares the outcomes of various erosion rate models for the L1-ML and L1-CL layer for the LH1 and LH2 hydraulic loading condition, respectively. The corresponding NRMSE values are presented in Table 3. There are several key observations in regards to the internal particle migration:

- The inclusion of $\overline{q_{cr}}$ was important to capture particle migration within layers. In Fig. 3, it can be seen that erosion commenced earlier in L1-ML for all other models. This had a drastic impact on the deposition behaviour, as can be observed for L1-CL. This impact is less pronounced in the LH2 cases (Fig. 4), as the initiation of particle migration occurred close to the start of the experiment.
- There is minimal difference between the outcomes for the [Cividini and Gioda \(2004\)](#) and [Uzuoka et al. \(2012\)](#) models, irrespective of the hydraulic loading condition. This is also evident when comparing the NRMSE for L1-ML and L1-CL in Table 3, which are nearly identical for these two models. From Table 1, it can be seen that the only functional difference is the $(1 - \phi)$ term. This suggests that density plays a minimal role in the erosion rate model. This is likely the case for the underfilled gap-graded soils considered in this study, but may not be the case for transitional and overfilled fabrics, which were not tested in this study.
- The absence of an ultimate fines content ($f_{c\infty}$) in the [Khalil et al. \(2013\)](#) model indicates that erosion process would continue indefinitely. While this is not easily observed in the LH2 cases due to the relatively short experimental duration, it is more clear for the LH1 cases. In L1-ML, all other models show a slight reduction in the erosion rate towards the end of the experiment, while the outcomes for the

[Khalil et al. \(2013\)](#) model shows erosion continuing at the same rate. [Sterpi \(2003\)](#) attained close to the ultimate fines content in experiments that ran for up to 50 hours. Given that the experiments in this study were conducted to a maximum of 5 hours, it is unlikely that the ultimate fines content was reached. Nevertheless, this highlights that $f_{c\infty}$ is an important consideration.

Figure 3: Fines content in the L1-ML and L1-CL layers in the LH1 cases.

Figure 4: Fines content in the L1-ML and L1-CL layers in the LH2 cases.

Table 3: NRMSE for fines content in the L1-ML and L1-CL layer for various erosion rate models

Erosion Rate Model	FC15_LH1		FC20_LH1		FC25_LH1		FC15_LH2		FC20_LH2		FC25_LH2	
	L1-ML	L1-CL										
This Study	6.2	17.0	5.6	4.2	3.0	4.8	5.9	13.4	5.7	8.4	6.7	5.6
Khalil et al. (2013)	9.3	23.6	5.7	4.9	3.3	3.3	7.3	12.4	8.0	9.1	8.8	6.6
Cividini and Giorda (2004)	10.9	27.3	4.2	5.8	2.7	4.0	5.6	13.1	5.8	7.5	7.8	5.5
Uzuoka et al. (2012)	10.2	26.8	4.2	5.9	2.6	4.3	5.9	12.3	5.9	7.5	7.6	5.3

1.2 Deposition Rate Model

The various deposition rate models considered in this study are reproduced in Table 4. As unidirectional volume exchange is considered in the ML and CL, the erosion rate model considered in this study is applied to the ML, and the various deposition rate models are applied to the CL. As such, the consideration of various deposition rate models will not affect the ML, and therefore, the following results focus on the impact of the deposition rate models on the CL and layers within the CL.

Table 4: Deposition Rate Models

Source	Deposition Rate
This Study	$\hat{n}_d = \lambda_d \left(1 - \frac{\phi_{\min}}{\phi}\right) c \bar{q}_w ^{1/2}$
Schauffler et al. (2013)	$\hat{n}_d = \lambda_d c \bar{q}_w $
Vardoulakis et al. (1996)	$\hat{n}_d = \lambda_d (1 - \phi) c \bar{q}_w $
Steeb et al. (2007)	$\hat{n}_d = \lambda_d (1 - \phi) c \bar{q}_w ^2$
Yang et al. (2019)	$\hat{n}_d = \lambda_d \frac{\phi - \phi_{\min}}{\phi^\beta} c \bar{q}_w $

Fig. 5 compares the outcome of various deposition rate models for the evolution of fines contents in the CL. Broadly, all deposition rate models capture the macro-scale filtration behaviour in the CL across all three fines content. This is reflected in the NRMSE values in Table 5, which range from 2.7-4.9%. Similarly, the deposition rate models can capture the filtration behaviour for the higher hydraulic loading condition, as shown in Fig. 6. There are some notable differences for the LH2 cases. For FC20_LH2, the initial burst of filtration is not well captured by any of the models (with NRMSE values ranging from 5.8-6.9%), although a better fit is noted at the end of the simulation. For FC25_LH2, the complete mixture condition at approximately 100 minutes leading to a rapid transition is also not well captured. Nevertheless, the various deposition rate models broadly match

the macro-scale response of the CL with a NRMSE value less than 5%.

Despite the close match in the macro-scale response, the behaviour of the deposition rate models differs significantly when we consider individual layers with the CL. Figs. 7-8 shows the evolution of fines content in all five layers of the CL across for the LH1 and LH2 hydraulic conditions, respectively. The respective NRMSE values for each layer is listed in Tables 6-7. The key observations are summarised below:

- The staggered response from L1-CL to L5-CL is clearly visible for all cases with significantly more deposition occurring in L1-CL, which gradually reduces until L5-CL. The experimental data for L5-CL should be interpreted with caution, as they are highly affected by the permittivity difference with the overlying water column.
- Overall, when considering all the NRMSE values in Tables 6-7, the deposition rate model presented in this paper performs the best for both the LH1 and LH2 conditions. The performance was also generally better for the LH1 conditions, which reinforces that gradual particle migration is better captured by the presented continuum approach. This also highlights that both the adjusted time-scale (i.e. $\bar{q}_w^{-1/2}$) and the minimum porosity (ϕ_{\min}) are important elements of the deposition rate model.
- The outcomes for the [Schauffer et al. \(2013\)](#) and [Vardoulakis et al. \(1996\)](#) deposition rate models are very similar when considering the CL as a whole, as well as when considering layers within the CL. This suggests that the density term, $1 - \phi$, does not play a significant role. These two models are also similar to [Steeb et al. \(2007\)](#) when there is only a small amount of filtration (i.e. less than 5%, which can usually be observed in L3-CL and above).
- The [Schauffer et al. \(2013\)](#), [Vardoulakis et al. \(1996\)](#), and [Steeb et al. \(2007\)](#) models do not consider a limiting porosity (ϕ_{\min}). As such, the fines content can continue to increase indefinitely in these models, which can result in non-physical porosity

values. This is most notable in L1-CL. For example, for the FC20.LH1 case, these three deposition rate models show the fines content increasing to well above 10% in the L1-CL layer, differing significantly from the plateau noted in the experimental data.

- The [Yang et al. \(2019\)](#) deposition rate model accurately captures the plateau in fines content within each layer through the inclusion of the ϕ_{\min} term. However, it fails to capture the steep initial increase as particles enter the layer, and instead shows a more gradual build-up of the filtration process. This reinforces the importance of the adjusted time-scale through the $\bar{q}_w^{-1/2}$ term.

Figure 5: Fines content in the CL for the LH1 cases. The results for each deposition rate model considered in this study are distinctly shown.

Figure 6: Fines content in the CL for the LH2 cases.

Table 5: NRMSE for fines content in the CL for various deposition rate models

Deposition Rate Model	FC15_LH1	FC20_LH1	FC25_LH1	FC15_LH2	FC20_LH2	FC25_LH2
This Study	4.7	2.9	2.7	3.5	5.8	4.8
Schauffer et al. (2013)	3.6	2.8	2.6	2.8	6.1	5.6
Vardoulakis et al. (1996)	3.5	3.0	2.7	2.7	6.3	5.7
Steeb et al. (2007)	3.5	4.9	4.2	2.8	6.9	7.4
Yang et al. (2019)	4.0	2.7	2.6	2.9	6.2	5.7

Figure 7: Fines content in the layers of the CL for the LH1 cases.

Figure 8: Fines content in the layers of the CL for the LH2 cases.

Table 6: NRMSE for fines content in the CL for the LH1 cases for various deposition rate models

Deposition Rate Model	FC15_LH1					FC20_LH1					FC25_LH1				
	L1	L2	L3	L4	L5	L1	L2	L3	L4	L5	L1	L2	L3	L4	L5
This Study	17.0	7.3	7.8	6.6	9.3	4.2	3.9	3.1	5.2	4.3	4.8	2.9	3.9	2.2	8.3
Schauffer et al. (2013)	14.2	8.7	8.1	5.8	9.0	16.8	7.2	7.2	6.6	6.1	8.9	2.9	4.3	1.9	7.6
Vardoulakis et al. (1996)	12.8	9.6	8.4	5.8	9.0	16.5	7.4	7.5	7.0	6.4	9.4	3.2	4.1	1.9	7.6
Steeb et al. (2007)	14.1	9.7	8.6	5.9	8.9	15.2	9.7	8.4	7.1	6.3	14.6	6.8	2.3	1.6	7.6
Yang et al. (2019)	7.6	7.9	8.6	6.0	10.4	9.2	7.2	7.4	3.7	7.1	9.7	3.1	5.7	2.8	7.6

Table 7: NRMSE for fines content in the CL for the LH2 cases for various deposition rate models

Deposition Rate Model	FC15_LH2					FC20_LH2					FC25_LH2				
	L1	L2	L3	L4	L5	L1	L2	L3	L4	L5	L1	L2	L3	L4	L5
This Study	13.4	4.9	3.6	7.5	7.1	8.4	11.0	6.1	4.8	4.7	5.6	3.0	5.2	9.3	13.2
Schauffler et al. (2013)	9.5	6.5	5.2	4.6	7.9	16.0	13.8	8.9	5.2	3.7	9.4	4.6	7.5	9.8	12.3
Vardoulakis et al. (1996)	10.0	6.8	5.1	4.6	7.8	15.7	14.2	9.1	5.4	3.7	9.5	4.8	7.6	9.9	12.4
Steeb et al. (2007)	11.3	6.4	5.1	4.7	7.6	16.8	15.2	9.5	5.7	3.8	12.6	7.2	8.2	10.4	12.4
Yang et al. (2019)	9.2	7.6	5.6	4.9	10.1	13.2	14.8	9.6	3.3	9.6	11.0	5.4	7.3	7.3	10.1

References

- VS Ramakrishna Annapareddy, Adnan Sufian, Thierry Bore, and Alexander Scheuermann. Spatial and temporal evolution of particle migration in gap-graded granular soils: Insights from experimental observations. *Journal of Geotechnical and Geoenvironmental Engineering*, 149(3):04022135, 2023.
- Annamaria Cividini and Giancarlo Gioda. Finite-element approach to the erosion and transport of fine particles in granular soils. *International Journal of Geomechanics*, 4(3):191–198, 2004.
- Tony Khalil, Nadia Saiyouri, Bogdan Muresan, and Pierre-Yves Hicher. Internal erosion of chemically reinforced granular materials: a mathematical modeling approach. *International journal for numerical and analytical methods in geomechanics*, 37(5):491–502, 2013.
- Alexander Schaufler, Christian Becker, and Holger Steeb. Infiltration processes in cohesionless soils. *ZAMM-Journal of Applied Mathematics and Mechanics/Zeitschrift für Angewandte Mathematik und Mechanik*, 93(2-3):138–146, 2013.
- Holger Steeb, Stefan Diebels, and Ioannis Vardoulakis. Modeling internal erosion in porous media. In *Computer Applications In Geotechnical Engineering*, pages 1–10. 2007.
- Donatella Sterpi. Effects of the erosion and transport of fine particles due to seepage flow. *International journal of Geomechanics*, 3(1):111–122, 2003.
- Ryosuke Uzuoka, Tomohiro Ichiyama, Tomohiro Mori, and Motoki Kazama. Hydro-mechanical analysis of internal erosion with mass exchange between solid and water. *ICSE6 Paris*, pages 655–662, 2012.
- Ioannis Vardoulakis, Maria Stavropoulou, and Panos Papanastasiou. Hydro-mechanical aspects of the sand production problem. *Transport in porous media*, 22:225–244, 1996.

Jie Yang, Zhen-Yu Yin, Farid Laouafa, and Pierre-Yves Hicher. Modeling coupled erosion and filtration of fine particles in granular media. *Acta Geotechnica*, 14:1615–1627, 2019.